

Radiation Effect on the Astrometric Performance of Stars of $G \gtrsim 15$

prepared by: L. Lindegren, C. Crowley
approved by: F. van Leeuwen
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Abstract

The aim of this document is to provide an estimate of the degradation in the astrometric science performance due to radiation damage, after the application of the radiation calibration. These preliminary estimates are based on an analysis of a subset of Astrium experimental test data, the so-called ‘sky-like’ data obtained during Radiation Campaign#3. Due to constraints inherent in these data, estimates are not available for $G \lesssim 15$ and estimates are most reliable for $G \gtrsim 18$. An upper limit to the degradation factor for the faint stars is calculated to be to be 1.05 and increasing to 1.12 at $G = 17$ and 1.60 at $G = 15$. When these degradation factors are applied to baseline performance estimates we find that the EOM performance upper limit estimates do not yet meet specifications for the brighter stars, but do meet the required specifications for the faint stars. It is crucial to note that these upper limits (in particular for the brighter stars) are heavily dependent on inadequacies in the bias model, the quality of which is limited due to factors involving the design of the experimental test setup. A similar analysis of Radiation Campaign#4 data, with test conditions optimised for this analysis, will facilitate an improvement in the modelling, most likely driving down these upper limits (in particular for stars of magnitudes $15 \leq G \leq 18$).

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Acronyms

The following table has been generated from the on-line Gaia acronym list:

Acronym	Description
AC	ACross scan (direction)
AGIS	Astrometric Global Iterative Solution
AL	ALong scan (direction)
CCD	Charge-Coupled Device
CDM	Charge Distortion Model
CI	Charge Injection
CTI	Charge Transfer Inefficiency
DPAC	Data Processing and Analysis Consortium
IDT	Initial Data Treatment
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LSF	Line Spread Function
NIEL	Non-Ionising Energy Loss
RMS	Root-Mean-Square
TDI	Time-Delayed Integration (CCD)

1 Introduction

The damaging effects of radiation on the silicon structure of the Gaia detectors will result in the trapping, and subsequent delayed release, of electrons as they are transferred across the CCD during readout. This will result in a deformation of the image shape which implies a subsequent drop in the astrometric centroiding performance (as well as charge loss etc.). In order for the mission requirements to be met, these radiation-induced effects need to be mitigated against through calibration (as well as the other strategies, such as periodic charge injection to fill the empty traps). It is the aim of this document to provide an End of Mission (EOM) estimate of the degradation in the astrometric science performance due to radiation damage, after the application of the radiation calibration. This is a work-in-progress, the numbers outlined here were calculated in July 2010 and are based on an analysis of a subset of Astrium experimental test data.

The method of analysis is briefly discussed in Sect. 2 and a description of the models and results are outlined in Sect. 3. Upper limits on the performance degradation due to radiation are outlined in Sect. 4 and these degradation factors are then used to calculate EOM performance estimates which are presented in Sect. 5.

2 Overview of the Method

The performance estimates presented in this document are based on an analysis of the Astrium Radiation Campaign (RC) #3 astrometric ‘sky-like’ data (GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00415). These tests were designed to mimic a pseudo-realistic sky pattern being passed across the CCD through the use of a ‘sky-like’ mask (GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00423) which contains 1413 holes of 7 different diameters (see Fig. 1 for the geometry and flux response of the mask). The data delivery contains numerous datasets acquired with the mask passed over three different AC locations (including one ‘undamaged region’) of a partially irradiated detector. We use the term ZNI to denote the mask position over the undamaged region and the terms ZI1 and ZI2 to denote the two mask positions covering the damaged region. The tests were repeated with numerous combinations of parameters (such as illumination level, diffuse optical background level and charge injection settings). Each dataset contains 60 or 65 runs which are timed in order to provide an adequate sub-pixel sampling of the image shapes after co-addition. Most crucially, these data-acquisition settings were repeated with the mask rotated 180° w.r.t. to the CCD, which, in principle, allows the centroiding bias due to the CTI effects to be separated from calibration effects and from errors in the nominal positions of the holes on mask.

In order to demonstrate the feasibility of CTI mitigation for Gaia astrometric data, a recipe for an analysis of these test data was outlined in LL-082. This recipe was framed in the context of making as strong an analogy as possible between the test data and actual anticipated Gaia data. The central premise relies on testing the ability of the analysis to recover the actual hole

FIGURE 1: Magnitude distribution across the sky-like mask. This is a combination of a variation of the illumination level across the mask and the differing diameters of the holes. These data are generated from analysis of a test with the LED set to the brightest illumination level, where the nominal magnitude of the regularly-spaced calibration stars is $G = 15$.

positions on the mask despite the presence of traps in the detector. This is in much the same way that Gaia must recover the true positions of the stars on the sky with radiation-damaged detectors. The analogy can also be extended further. The mask rotation can be seen to correspond to the scanning of stars from differing directions over the course of the mission. The geometrical and optical calibrations are analogous to the attitude and large-scale calibration parameters that must be taken into account in the real Gaia data processing. Extending the analogy further, the preprocessing of the raw data produces information on the raw image parameters similar to that produced by IDT processing. This information is then used to solve for the desired unknown ‘stellar’ and calibration parameters (self-calibrating, like AGIS) by finding the best global match, in a weighted least-square sense, between the measured data and an observational model.

Of course, in order to examine the ability of the calibration to remove the effects of the radiation damage, a radiation bias-correction term must be included in the model. In this respect, the analysis strategy differs from that proposed by DPAC for Gaia, where the radiation-induced image shape distortion is corrected through the application of a calibrated CDM (see LL-075 and AS-015; for a description of the DPAC radiation mitigation strategy see FVL-006, FVL-059 and references within). In order to deal with extended sources, and also to correctly estimate

the formal centroiding errors, a CDM is required. In this proof-of-concept analysis, however, all ‘stars’ can be treated as point sources, so a bias correction term which is dependent on the G magnitude and the local charge injection history of the CCD suffices (not dissimilar to the Astrium CTI mitigation strategy, as outlined in GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00411). It should be noted that this analysis cannot provide performance estimates for bright stars, since there are few stars brighter than $G \sim 15$ in the dataset.

3 Analysis Overview

The reduction of the data was split into two separate stages. Stage 1 was an IDT-like processing of the raw data and stage 2 was an AGIS-like treatment of the output from stage 1. Both of these steps were experimental and iterative and the results presented here are most-likely not derived from the final iteration. Those results will appear in the form of two separate technical notes by C. Crowley and L. Lindegren, where a more complete description of the data analysis will be outlined.

3.1 Preprocessing of the Raw Data

After standard CCD data-processing techniques were applied to the raw data (bias removal, application of gain, removal of background, removal of slope due to CI (using the outer-most samples of the extraction window, as described in LL-069) etc.) the location and magnitude of each star in the appropriate TDI stream was estimated by use of Tukey’s Biweight (LL-069). A subset of the brightest stars located in the regular portion of the mask, and detected on the undamaged region of the CCD, was selected to be used to determine an approximate, mean LSF. These data were then normalised, aligned and co-added in order to facilitate fitting with a continuous function. The dominant contributant components from a list of the theoretically strongest Gaia LSF components (LL-084) were identified and their coefficients estimated in a weighted least-squares fit to the accumulated profiles. These coefficients were then used to construct a continuous LSF to be used in the estimation of the location and integrated flux of each star (both damaged and undamaged) in the dataset.

A maximum likelihood algorithm (LL-078) was utilised in order to fit the LSF to the central 14 samples of each image in each TDI stream. This procedure produced estimates of the location, flux and offset (due to offset non-uniformity, detector defects or overlapping wings of neighbouring profiles) of each image, together with an estimate of the formal centroiding error. This procedure also required an estimate of the readout noise, which was obtained using the 2-sigma clipped standard-deviation of the signal in the appropriate TDI stream before the mask passed over the detector. This information, as well as the time since CI for each star, along with numerous house-keeping parameters (i.e., AC location of each star on the CCD, flags indicating the possible influence of CCD artefacts etc.) was prepared for ingestion for processing in the AGIS-like solution.

3.2 Formulation and Application of the AGIS-like Model

In LL-082 it was foreseen to reduce the preprocessed data for the undamaged part of the CCD (ZNI) and the damaged part (ZI1+ZI2) separately, and derive the statistical increase in the residual noise (as quantified by the unit weight error) in the damaged part. This, however, would not allow the use of the same model in the two solutions. For example, the ZNI data only have one AC position of the mask, which means that stitching errors cannot be included in that solution. For this and other reasons it was considered advantageous to use *all* the data (NZI+ZI1+ZI2) in a single solution, with a much better handle on the stitching errors from the three mask positions, and instead introduce two sets of bias parameters: one valid in the damaged AC region (determined to correspond to CCD column number $1522 \leq m \leq 1773$) and the other parameter set valid in the undamaged region. (The transition region was found to be so sharp – a few pixels only – that it could effectively be ignored. Ideally, data for the corresponding pixel columns should be ignored, but that turned out to create problems for some stars. For the same reason, the known faulty columns were not removed in the present solutions.)

The first trial solutions used the data for all the holes, both in the regular and sky-like part of the mask. Although the regular part creates some problems in modelling due to self-injection, it was in practice necessary to include the regular mask to have sufficient AC coverage for each position of the mask. The regular mask also contains a large number of bright stars in a small magnitude range, which is problematic in an optimally weighted solution (because they dominate too much) and also in the results statistics. For these reasons we chose to reduce the number of stars actually used in the regular mask, by retaining only the first, last, and the two middle-most lines (see Fig. 2). For the retained regular stars, the time since charge injection (T) was set as follows: In each mask orientation, the leading line of stars had the value of T given by the previous CI, or 10,000 TDI periods if there was no charge injection. For the middle and last lines, it was assumed that self-injection effectively resulted in $T = 50$ TDI periods (the AL separation of the regular stars), or the actual time since CI if it was less than 50 TDI periods. The adopted analysis model is similar to the one in Eq. (2) of LL-082, with minor modifications resulting from trial-and-error analysis experiments. For example, it was found that the variation of the mask rotation between the different runs (jk) within a dataset (j) was quite small; hence the ‘attitude’ coefficients $a_{jk}^{(1)}$ representing different rotations for each run could be replaced by the ‘calibration’ coefficients $c_j^{(01)}$ representing a single rotation for each dataset (j). This gave a very significant reduction in the number of unknowns, at the expense of a modest increase in the unit weight error.

On the other hand, it was found desirable to include third-degree terms in the calibration polynomial (different for each dataset), and a linear variation of the AL error across each stitching block. To improve numerical conditioning, the calibration polynomial is written as a linear combination of Legendre polynomials in the normalized AL and AC coordinates.

FIGURE 2: Schematic diagram showing the stars used in both solutions, a large proportion of the regularly-spaced calibration stars were excluded.

For the bias term, depending on G and $\log T$ (where T is the time since the last CI), it was found that a generalized Astrium-type bias model, i.e., a 2D polynomial with up to cubic terms in G and quadratic in $\log T$ gave a rather satisfactory fit over the full range of G and T values in these data. However, this model, with a total of 12 parameters per region (undamaged and damaged), tends to be quite unstable especially in combination with all the other calibration and stitching parameters. To stabilize the solution, only a subset of the most significant polynomial terms was retained, at the expense of a slight increase in the unit weight error. The bias model finally adopted thus consists of the sum of a cubic polynomial in G and a linear polynomial in $\log T$, yielding 6 coefficients (parameters) in each region. One of these had to be constrained to zero to remove the degeneracy with respect to other unknowns (see below).

The resulting model (hereafter called model A) was therefore:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{ijk} - s_j x_i &= s_j \Delta x_i^{(0)} + a_{jk}^{(0)} \\
 &+ \sum_{\alpha=0}^3 \sum_{\beta=0}^3 c_j^{(\alpha\beta)} P_\alpha \left(\frac{s_j x_i}{x_{\max}} \right) P_\beta \left(\frac{s_j y_i}{y_{\max}} \right) \quad (1 \leq \alpha + \beta \leq 3) \\
 &+ d_s^{(0)} + d_s^{(1)} (m_{ijk} - m_s) \\
 &+ \sum_{\alpha=0}^3 b_r^{(\alpha 0)} \left(\frac{G_{ijk} - 15}{5} \right)^\alpha + b_r^{(01)} (\log_{10} T_{ijk} - 2.5) \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The unknowns on the right-hand side are:

- $\Delta x_i^{(0)}$ is the correction to the nominal AL position of star i on the mask;
- $a_{jk}^{(0)}$ is the ‘attitude’ parameter in run jk , representing the AL origin of the run;

- $c_j^{(\alpha\beta)}$ are ‘large-scale calibration’ parameters in dataset j representing optical distortions that may vary between datasets;
- $d_s^{(0)}$ and $d_s^{(1)}$ are the AL offset and slope of stitching block s , relative to its central AC position m_s ;
- $b_r^{(\alpha\beta)}$ are parameters of the bias model for CCD region r ($r = 1$ for the undamaged and $r = 2$ for the damaged region), depending on the powers α and β of G and $\log T$, respectively.

In order to render the solution non-singular, linear constraints were added as discussed in LL-082. The total number of constraints for the above model is 13. One of these is $b_1^{(00)} = 0$, which fixes the zero point of the bias function at $G = 15$ and $\log_{10} T = 2.5$ in the undamaged zone. The total number of parameters (including the constrained ones) is 5249.

3.2.1 Solution for model A

The solution for model A used a total of 2,994,553 observations (in 62 datasets with 3816 runs), of which 21,458 were rejected as outliers. The outliers were identified by an iterative procedure, where the rejection limit was successively brought down to 20 times the formal standard deviation of the observation, multiplied by the unit weight error of the solution. Observations with $G < 12$, $G > 21$, or $\sigma > 0.1$ TDI period had been rejected a priori.

The overall unit weight error (square root of the chi-square divided by the number of degrees of freedom) was $U_A = 1.682022$, which is unacceptably high.

Inspection of the residuals shows that there is a very systematic variation from star to star, so that the dispersion of residuals for any given star is typically much smaller than the overall dispersion. Plotting the mean residual per star as a function of x_i (AL position on the mask) reveals a very strong signature (Fig. 3 (left)). In this plot the stars on the regular part of the mask (plotted in blue) appears to behave slightly differently from those in the sky-like mask (red), but this probably only reflects their different y coordinates. Plotting the median residual as a function of position (x, y) on the mask (Fig. 3 (right)) indicates that it is really an effect depending (mainly) on (x, y) – there is no visible discontinuity between the regular and sky-like parts. (This is confirmed by solutions including all the regular stars.)

We do not know the physical origin of the effect described above, and therefore we will call it the X effect for the remainder of this paper. The X effect represents a systematic shift in the TDI stream that always has the same sign for a given star, or rather for the same position on the mask. It is therefore not linked to the magnitude of the star or the time since CI (we anyway solve for such dependences in the bias term). One possible explanation is that the mask geometry, or the optical distortions, changed slightly (by up to 0.05 pixel) between the two orientations. This

FIGURE 3: **Left:** Mean residual per star as a function of x_i (AL position on the mask). **Right:** Median residual per star as a function of position (x, y) on the mask. Note the lack of any obvious discontinuity between the regular and sky-like portions.

is not impossible, given the relatively long time (about a month) between the measurements with mask up and down, or the circumstance that the mask (and part of the optics?) had to be dismantled and then mounted again between the two series of measurements. In any case the X effect is clearly a significant problem in the current analysis, mainly because it could hide more subtle effects that we are looking for.

FIGURE 4: **Left:** Mean residual plotted against AC coordinate, m , of the CCD. The red vertical lines indicate the location of the stitching block boundaries on the detector. Note that the damaged region extends from $m = 1522$ through 1773. **Right:** Unit weight error plotted against m .

Apart from this problem, the solution is rather satisfactory, see for example plots of the mean residual (Fig. 4 (left)) and unit weight error (Fig. 4 (right)) versus AC coordinate m . In these figures the red vertical lines indicate the boundaries of the stitching blocks; the damaged region extends from $m = 1522$ through 1773. Figures 5 (left) and 5 (right) show the same quantities

FIGURE 5: **Left:** Mean residual plotted against G magnitude. Note that in both of these plots the black curve corresponds to the undamaged region and red to the damaged region. **Right:** Unit weight error plotted against G .

plotted versus G magnitude. In the former figure one can see that the curves for the undamaged (black) and damaged (red) regions show similar patterns, except for the faintest stars. This is probably caused by the X effect, causing, for example, a number of $G = 18$ mag stars to have similar (negative) residuals in both regions. In Fig. 5 (right) it is seen that the bright stars have very large unit weight errors (~ 4 – 6 even in the undamaged region, while for the faintest stars it is a more reasonable ~ 1.2 – 1.5). This mainly reflects that the bright stars have much smaller formal standard errors (σ), so that even if the residuals are of a similar absolute size for the bright and faint stars, they would give a much larger unit weight error for the bright stars than for the faint. Indeed, if the RMS residuals (not normalized by the formal standard errors) are instead plotted versus G , we see that they increase towards the fainter stars (Fig. 6 (left)), both in the undamaged and damaged regions. The difference between the two curves in Fig. 6 (left) can in fact be used as an absolute measure of the residual CTI effects (see Sect. 4).

The bias solutions for the undamaged and damaged regions are

$$b_1(G, T) = 0.0000 + 0.0024g - 0.0078g^2 + 0.0239g^3 - 0.0054t \quad (\text{undamaged region}) \quad (2)$$

$$b_2(G, T) = 0.0382 - 0.0018g + 0.0398g^2 + 0.0402g^3 + 0.0079t \quad (\text{damaged region}) \quad (3)$$

where $g = (G - 15)/5$ and $t = \log_{10} T - 2.5$. Figures 7 (left) and 7 (right) are 2D plots of these functions. In the undamaged region the dependence on T unexpectedly has a negative sign. It appears to be significant, but could possibly be caused by other (unmodelled) effects. From a comparison with several other solutions it is clear that there is a quite significant G dependence for the faintest stars in the undamaged region, but it might be rather independent of T . In the damaged region, the combination of G and T dependence is as expected. The curves in Fig. 6 (right) show the bias function versus T for $G = 14.8, 18.4$ and 19.8 . These magnitudes were chosen to allow simple comparison with Astrium results (e.g., in GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00447). The results are comparable in trend and size, although we find much larger shifts for bright stars

FIGURE 6: **Left:** RMS residual plotted against the magnitude, G . Note that since these values are not normalized by the formal standard errors they increase with G . Also note that in both of these plots the black curve corresponds to the undamaged region and red to the damaged region. **Right:** The bias function versus T for $G = 14.8, 18.4$ and 19.8 are in the order from bottom up. These magnitudes were chosen to allow simple comparison with Astrium results.

with small T . This might be related to the chosen (linear) parameterisation in terms of $\log T$.

FIGURE 7: 2D plots of the bias functions applied to data from the the undamaged (left) and damaged (right) regions of the detector.

A check of the adopted bias model is obtained by mapping the median residual as a function of G and T . The results are shown in Fig. 8 (left) for the undamaged and in Fig. 8 (right) for the damaged region. There are clearly systematic deviations from the bias model at the level of 0.01–0.02 TDI periods, but they would not explain the discrepancy with respect to the Astrium results for small T . This can better be appreciated by means of Figs. 9 (left) and 9 (right), which plot the sum of the fitted bias function and the median residuals from the previous plots. These plots are probably the most faithful descriptions of the bias effect as a function of G and T based on the current data and solutions. They support the tentative conclusion above, namely that in

the undamaged region there is an effect of G for the faintest stars, but no dependence on T , while in the damaged region the effect depends on both variables in a fairly complex way. The behaviour at the very shortest T (10 to 16 TDI periods) is very uncertain and could be strongly affected by the background slope determination.

FIGURE 8: Maps of the median residual as a function of G and T for the undamaged (left) and damaged (right) regions.

FIGURE 9: The sum of the fitted bias function and the median residuals (as shown in Figs. 7 and 8) for the undamaged (left) and damaged (right) regions. These plots are probably the most faithful descriptions of the bias effect as a function of G and T based on the current data and solutions and suggest that in the undamaged region there is a dependence on G for the faintest stars, but no dependence on T , while in the damaged region the effect depends on both variables in a fairly complex way.

3.2.2 Solution for model B

In model B we introduce, on a purely ad hoc basis and without any theoretical justification, one more unknown for each star, namely its mean shift $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$ in the AL direction. Thus, instead of

the first line of Eq. (1) we have:

$$u_{ijk} - s_j x_i = s_j \Delta x_i^{(0)} + \Delta x_i^{(1)} + a_{jk}^{(0)} + \dots \quad (4)$$

This drastically reduces the unit weight error to $U_B = 1.286782$. The number of observations is, as before, 2,994,553 observations, of which 21,536 were rejected as outliers. The number of parameters is 6102, and the number of constraints 23 (ten more constraints are needed to eliminate degeneracies between the attitude and calibration parameters and the new star parameters). However, although this model gives much better fit, it is physically not very useful, because the new parameters may absorb some of the effects that we are looking for. In particular the G dependence of the CTI shift is to a large extent taken up by the new star parameters, since a given star (with a fixed $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$ has nearly the same G in all its observations. The resulting bias solution is therefore not very relevant. On the other hand, the residuals plotted against m , for example, look much better (i.e., compare Fig. 12 with Fig. 4). For completeness and to allow this comparison, we show in Figs. 11 through 17 exactly the same kind of plots as was shown in Figs. 3 through 9 for model A. The bias solution for model B is

$$b_1(G, T) = 0.0000 + 0.1321g - 0.0429g^2 - 0.0207g^3 - 0.0022t \quad (\text{undamaged region}) \quad (5)$$

$$b_2(G, T) = 0.0357 + 0.1428g - 0.0297g^2 + 0.0191g^3 + 0.0126t \quad (\text{damaged region}) \quad (6)$$

although, as explained above, this bias function (and the corresponding Figs. 14 (right)–17) do not make much sense physically.

3.3 Excess noise in the damaged region

The panels on the left-hand side of Figures 6 (model A) and 14 (model B) show the RMS residuals in the undamaged and damaged regions as functions of magnitude. In each diagram, the difference between the two curves (computed as the square root of the difference between the squares) indicates the excess RMS residual caused by unmodelled effects of the radiation damage. In principle, one expects that this calculation should yield roughly the same result for different models, as long as the bias modelling is the same. Thus the same result is expected from model A and B, in spite of the fact that B gives a much better overall fit.

This conjecture is put to the test in Fig. 10, where the red curve shows the excess RMS residual derived in model A, and the blue curve shows the excess noise in model B. The black dashed curve is the theoretically computed standard error from JDB-053 (AF2–9); these standard errors are about 5–15% larger than the formal errors obtained from the LSF fitting to the RC#3 test data (dotted line). Within the statistical uncertainties, it does indeed appear that the excess noise, as function of magnitude, is the same for the two models. It is therefore reasonable to assume that the red and blue curves in Fig. 10 describe the real CTI modelling errors in these solutions.

FIGURE 10: The red curve shows the excess RMS residual derived in model A, and the blue curve shows the excess noise in model B. The dashed black curve is the theoretically computed standard error from JDB-053 (AF2–9) and the dotted black curve is the mean formal standard deviation obtained from the LSF fitting to the data. Note that the excess noise, as function of magnitude, appears to be the same for the two models within the statistical uncertainties. It seems reasonable to assume that the red and blue curves describe the real CTI modelling errors in these solutions (see text for details).

4 Estimates of Astrometric Performance Degradation Due to Radiation

It is possible to directly estimate upper limits on the radiation-induced degradation in the centroiding and astrometric accuracies from Fig. 10. This is achieved by comparing the relative difference between the CTI modelling error and the theoretical standard error on the centroiding for a particular value of G . It should be noted that the results presented in Fig. 10 correspond to a NIEL dose of $4 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

From Fig. 10 we conclude that the CTI effects contribute an RMS noise of about 0.01 TDI periods for $G \lesssim 17$, increasing to about 0.6 times the formal localisation error for faint magnitudes. A likely interpretation for the plateau for the brighter stars is that this is caused by an inadequate bias model which used in this analysis. The observed increase for fainter magnitudes is likely caused by the statistical difficulty in calibrating the bias function to significantly better than the photon-statistical errors. With an improved bias model it is likely that the plateau (for the brighter stars) can be reduced, possibly by a very significant factor. Also, with more observations per (G, T) cell, for example, it is likely that the factor 0.6 (for the faint stars) could be brought down somewhat. In both cases, therefore, the present results represent only upper

limits to what could reasonably be achieved in the real mission. An optimised test setup for the next round of ‘sky-like’ experiments will likely result in a much-improved bias model, in particular for the brighter stars.

In terms of the astrometric accuracy, the radiation-induced degradation factor for the faint stars ($G \gtrsim 19$) is therefore, at most, $\sqrt{1 + 0.6^2} = 1.17$. Since a NIEL dose of $4 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ is higher than the expected real EOM dose, it is more informative to consider the degradation effects of a more realistic dose of half of that which was applied to the detector used in RC#3. If the CTI effects are directly proportional to the NIEL dose, and we assume an EOM dose of $2 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, we obtain instead a degradation factor of 1.05 for the same magnitude range. Similarly, the degradation factor estimates for stars of magnitudes $15 \leq G \leq 21$ are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2: Estimated astrometric performance degradation factors due to radiation got differing G magnitudes.

G	Radiation Degradation (NIEL $\sim 4 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	Radiation Degradation (NIEL $\sim 2 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$)
15	2.7	1.60
16	1.9	1.28
17	1.4	1.12
18	1.26	1.07
$\gtrsim 19$	1.17	1.05

5 Implications for the EOM Astrometric Performance

Using the estimated upper limits for the radiation-induced degradation factors presented in Sect. 4, it is possible estimate upper limits on the EOM astrometric performance. In order to calculate these estimates we apply the radiation degradation factors (calculated for a NIEL dose of $2 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$) to the end-of-life parallax performance estimates presented in Table 3 of JDB-055 (with no radiation bias effect considered). These values are presented in units of μas in Table 3 (in the final column). The EOM performance specifications and current Astrium estimates (from GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00486) for the same spectral types are also presented for ease of comparison.

It is important to note that future experiments, using data from RC#4, should be able to refine the bias model considerably, and thus reduce the degradation upper limit estimates (and, obviously, also the EOM performance upper limit estimates), in particular for the brighter stars.

TABLE 3: Upper limits for the EOM astrometric performance (in units of μas) as derived in this analysis. These values were calculated by applying the radiation-induced degradation factors described in Sect. 4 to baseline performance estimates from JDB-055 (and also assuming a NIEL dose of $2 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$). For comparison, the mission requirement specifications are outlined for the same stellar spectral types, along with the current estimates from Astrium (GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00486). It should be noted these upper limits from this present analysis are heavily dependent on inadequacies in the bias model (in particular for the brighter stars) and that this bias model should be improved substantially after the reduction of the RC#4 ‘sky-like’ dataset.

Spectral Type	V-mag	G-mag	Specification	Astrium	Present Analysis
B1V	15	15	< 25	26.3	< 33.9
	20	20	< 300	326.3	< 298
G2V	15	14.8	< 24	24.2	< 32
	20	19.8	< 300	290.2	< 272
M6V	20	17.7	< 100	96.6	< 87

6 Conclusions and Future

Based on an analysis of the Astrium RC#3 ‘sky-like’ data, we estimate upper limits to the radiation-induced degradation in the astrometric performance for stars of magnitude $G \gtrsim 15$. Assuming CTI effects directly proportional to the NIEL dose, and a NIEL dose of $2 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the degradation factor for the faint stars is estimated to be 1.05 and increasing to 1.12 at $G = 17$ and 1.60 at $G = 15$. When these degradation factors are applied to baseline performance estimates, we find that the EOM performance upper limit estimates do not yet meet specifications for the brighter stars, but do meet the required specifications for the faint stars (see Table 3). We emphasise that these are upper limits which depend on the inadequacies of the present bias model.

Similar sky-like tests are planned for RC#4, with the test setup being optimised for this analysis. Reduction of these data should facilitate an improved model and considerably reduce these upper limits, in particular for stars of magnitudes $15 \leq G \leq 18$. The possibility of incorporating a CDM into this analysis is also being examined. Further estimates (including those for bright stars) will be forthcoming from an analysis of other test data; this analysis is currently underway.

7 References

[JDB-055], de Bruijne, J., 2009, *Gaia astrometric performance. Summer 2009 status*,

GAIA-CA-TN-ESA-JDB-055,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2939503>

[JDB-053], de Bruijne, J., 2009, *ALong- and ACross-scan location-estimation performance*,

GAIA-CA-TN-ESA-JDB-053,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2913726>

[GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00411], EADS Astrium, 2009, *Implementation of the Astrium radiation calibration strategy for astrometry*,

GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00411,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2907681>

[GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00415], EADS Astrium, 2009, *Radiation campaign #3. Astrometric sky-like data delivery*,

GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00415,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2899661>

[GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00423], EADS Astrium, 2009, *Astrometric sky-like mask design*,

GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00423,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2899656>

[GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00447], EADS Astrium, 2009, *Radiation campaign #3. Astrium astrometric regular test report*,

GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00447,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2961322>

[GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00486], EADS Astrium, 2010, *Science Performance Budget Report, Issue 4, Rev. 0*,

GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00486

[LL-069], Lindegren, L., 2007, *Simplified centroiding algorithm for radiation test data*,

GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-069,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2742592>

[LL-075], Lindegren, L., 2008, *Modelling radiation damage effects for Gaia - A first-order Charge Distortion Model (CDM-01)*,

GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-075,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2824544>

[LL-078], Lindegren, L., 2008, *A general Maximum-Likelihood algorithm for model fitting to CCD sample data*,

GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-078,

URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelihood/open/2861864>

[LL-082], Lindegren, L., 2009, *Demonstrating the feasibility of a CTI mitigation strategy for astrometry using astrometric sky-like test data*,

GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-082,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2907018>

[**LL-084**], Lindegren, L., 2009, *Minimum-dimension LSF modelling*,
GAIA-C3-TN-LU-LL-084,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2915742>

[**AS-015**], Short, A., 2009, *Charge Distortion Model 02 (CDM02)*,
GAIA-CH-TN-ESA-AS-015,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2882372>

[**FVL-059**], van Leeuwen, F., 2010, *Status of the DPAC CTI mitigation in June 2010*,
GAIA-C5-TN-IOA-FVL-059,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/3035697>

[**FVL-006**], van Leeuwen, F., Lindegren, L., 2007, *Outline of the Radiation Calibration Strategy for Astrometry, Photometry and Spectroscopy*,
GAIA-C5-TN-IOA-FVL-006,
URL <http://www.rssd.esa.int/llink/livelink/open/2775637>

APPENDIX

A Plots from Solution to Model B

This appendix contains plots pertaining to the solution to model B, as outlined in Sect. 3.2.2. These plots are directly comparable to Figs. 3 through 9 which correspond to the solution to model A.

FIGURE 11: These plots are the model B counterparts to those in Fig. 3. **Left:** Mean residual per star as a function of x_i (AL position on the mask). **Right:** Median residual per star as a function of position (x, y) on the mask.

FIGURE 12: These plots are the model B counterparts to those in Fig. 4. Mean residual plotted against AC coordinate, m , of the CCD. The red vertical lines indicate the location of the stitching block boundaries on the detector. Note that the damaged region extends from $m = 1522$ through 1773. **Right:** Unit weight error plotted against m .

FIGURE 13: These plots are the model B counterparts to those in Fig. 5. Mean residual plotted against G magnitude. Note that in both of these plots the black curve corresponds to the undamaged region and red to the damaged region. The scale of the y-axis is in units of 10^{-3} TDI periods. **Right:** Unit weight error plotted against G .

FIGURE 14: These plots are the model B counterparts to those in Fig. 6. **Left:** RMS residual plotted against the magnitude, G . Note that in both of these plots the black curve corresponds to the undamaged region and red to the damaged region. **Right:** The bias function versus T for $G = 14.8, 18.4$ and 19.8 are in the order from bottom up. Note that this bias solution is distorted by the presence in model B of the $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$ terms, which absorb part of the image shifts.

FIGURE 15: These plots are the model B counterparts to those in Fig. 7. 2D plots of the bias functions applied to data from the the undamaged (left) and damaged (right) regions of the detector. Note that these bias solutions are distorted by the presence in model B of the $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$ terms, which absorb part of the image shifts.

FIGURE 16: These plots are the model B counterparts to those in Fig. 8. Shown are maps of the median residual as a function of G and T for the undamaged (left) and damaged (right) regions. Note that the bias solutions used in this case are distorted by the presence in model B of the $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$ terms, which absorb part of the image shifts.

FIGURE 17: These plots are the model B counterparts to those in Fig. 9. Plotted are the sum of the fitted bias function and the median residuals (as shown in Figs. 15 and 16 for the undamaged (left) and damaged (right) regions). Note that the bias solutions used in this case are distorted by the presence in model B of the $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$ terms, which absorb part of the image shifts.